

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV

**Actionable
version**

Definition

This summary provides actionable direction for researchers and research organisations to adopt narrative CVs that reflect Open Science values, build transparency, and enable fairer, more holistic researcher assessment.

A narrative CV is a structured format that allows researchers to present their achievements and contributions in a qualitative, evidence-based way. Unlike traditional lists of publications or grants, narrative CVs describe the researcher's wider impact on knowledge, people, communities, and society.

Evidence means showing the reach, use, and relevance of research contributions.

- Examples: citations, altmetrics, downloads, reviews, translations, dataset reuse, FAIR compliance, persistent identifiers (preferably with persistent identifiers like DOIs, ORCID).

Open Science (OS) (UNESCO 2021) is about making research inclusive, equitable, and accessible across four pillars:

1. Open scientific knowledge
2. Open science infrastructures
3. Open engagement of societal actors
4. Open dialogue with other knowledge systems

Relevant SCOPE stages

This guide is most relevant for:

- O – Options for evaluating: Identifying diverse contributions beyond publications.
- P – Probe deeply: Gathering robust, evidence-based examples of Open Science practices.

When and how to use

When:

- In recruitment, promotion, and funding decisions where a broader view of contributions is needed.
- When aligning with CoARA, DORA, or other RRA reform initiatives.

How:

- Give guidance to researchers on how to use narrative CV templates (e.g., Royal Society's [Résumé for Researchers](#) or UKRI's [R4RI](#)).
- Train evaluators to recognize OS contributions and assess them with equal weight.
- Use Figure 1 (below) to map activities across modules.

Guidance

Figure 1. Potential OS activities across narrative CV modules

Module 1 – Knowledge

- Prompt: How have you contributed to generating knowledge?
- Tips: Demonstrate transparency in data, methods, and results. Explain responsible limits (e.g., only sharing metadata for sensitive data).
- UNESCO pillar link: Open scientific knowledge.
- Examples: Open access papers, preprints, datasets (FAIR), shared code/software, multilingual outputs.

Module 2 – People

- Prompt: How have you contributed to the development of individuals?
- Tips: Show how you mentor, train, or support others in adopting OS practices. Highlight inclusivity in supervision and teamwork.
- UNESCO pillar link: Open scientific knowledge, open engagement of societal actors, open dialogue.
- Examples: Open educational resources, OS training, mentoring early-career researchers, publishing co-author statements.

Module 3 – Community

- Prompt: How have you contributed to the research community?

- Tips: Highlight service roles and community leadership in OS.
- UNESCO pillar link: Open science infrastructures.
- Examples: Open peer review, editing for OA journals, OS networks, multilingual scholarly communication, developing OS policies/guidelines.

Module 4 – Society

- Prompt: How have you contributed to broader society?
- Tips: Document non-academic dissemination, citizen engagement, and partnerships beyond academia.
- UNESCO pillar link: Open engagement of societal actors, open dialogue with knowledge systems.
- Examples: Public engagement, participatory science, multilingual communication, open innovation, recognition of citizen contributions.

Further reading

SCOPE+i Resources

- Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>
- Indicators guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>
- Open science assessment guide <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>
- Guide on diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089>

Other

- The Royal Society. Résumé for Researchers. <https://royalsociety.org/news-resources/projects/research-culture/tools-for-support/resume-for-researchers/>
- UKRI (2022). Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI) template. <https://www.ukri.org/publications/resume-for-research-and-innovation-r4ri-template/>
- DORA Resource Library: Narrative CV guidance <https://sfedora.org/resource-library/?keyword=narrative>
- University of Oxford: Guidance on developing narrative CVs
<https://researchsupport.admin.ox.ac.uk/learn-more-about-developing-a-narrative-cv>
- Maastricht University Library: Evidence-based narrative CV guide
<https://library.maastrichtuniversity.nl/research/evaluating-research/research-intelligence/narrative-cv/>
- RoRI (2025): Implementing Narrative CVs: Five Recommendations for Funders
<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28524755.v1>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

